

Bioplatforms Australia Framework Initiative Data & Collaboration Policy

Document History

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1. Purpose

This policy ensures that data created through the Bioplatforms Australia Science Program is managed and shared effectively. It aims to maximise the value of the data by making it accessible to the scientific community and supporting Australia's national research priorities. The policy promotes responsible data management to ensure the data can be used effectively to address key research challenges and drive scientific progress.

2. Roles and Responsibilities

- **Bioplatforms Australia:** Oversees program governance, data management, and access. Provides funding and coordination through the National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS).
 - **Bioplatforms Project Manager:** Supports the Project Team in planning, metadata standards, and data access approvals. First point of contact for questions about data sharing and collaboration.
 - **Project Lead:** Principal investigator. Responsible for delivering the project outcomes, providing metadata, and managing sensitive data where required.
 - **Project Partners:** Collaborators supporting the Project Lead in achieving agreed outcomes. May include data contributors, sample providers, and data users.
 - **Project Team:** Refers collectively to the Project Lead and Project Partners.
 - **Bioplatforms 'Omics Facilities:** Partner organisations that generate data in collaboration with the Project Team and transfer data to the Bioplatforms Data Portal.
 - **Bioplatforms Data Portal Team:** Manages secure storage and controlled access to the data. Operates the Data Portal infrastructure.
 - **Consortium Members:** Individuals or organisations that have contributed meaningfully to the scientific and operational aspects of the Initiative. May include Project Leads, Project Partners, or others involved in working groups, governance, or data use.
 - **General Data Users:** Anyone accessing the data after it is made publicly available, including external researchers or other stakeholders.
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3. Data Management & Sharing

3.1. Projects

Projects will be established through an open call for project proposals (Requests for Partnerships, RFP) based on a set of priorities, or through targeted engagement with community and/or advisory groups.

Datasets will be created under agreed projects, and will include a Project Lead and Project Partners (the Project Team). The Project Team, with support from the Bioplatforms Australia Project Manager and 'Omics Facilities, will define the experimental design suitable for the project aims. Samples will be prepared for extraction (e.g., DNA, RNA) by the Project Team and sent to the relevant 'Omics Facilities for sequencing/processing.

3.2. Raw Data Management and Storage

3.2.1. Data files

Following production, the 'omics facility will transfer the data files to the Bioplatforms Australia Data Portal, where they will be shared directly with the Project Team for primary access (see Section 3.3. Data Sharing Schedule). These data, alongside the metadata (described in Section 3.2.2.), will be accessible and downloadable by authorised users via the web interface and/or the Data Portal Application Programming Interface (API).

The Bioplatforms Australia Data Portal¹ is a password-secured central data repository managed by the Australian BioCommons via the Queensland Cyber Infrastructure Foundation (QCIF) at the University of Queensland, Brisbane². This database is hosted at Amazon Web Services (AWS) in Sydney, with a mirrored backup at QRIS-Cloud in Brisbane to ensure disaster recovery capabilities.

3.2.2. Metadata

Metadata will be provided by the Project Lead in an agreed standardised format (provided by the Bioplatforms Project Manager). This metadata will be openly available, except where sensitive information is involved (see Section 3.2.3).

Metadata will include contextual information on the specimen/sample, methods for material extraction, sample library preparation, and 'omics data generation.

3.2.3. Consideration for sensitive information

Bioplatforms is committed to ensuring that data generated through the Initiative is predominantly open access, with appropriate community embargo periods (as described in Section 3.3), to maximise scientific reuse and benefit. However, we recognise that some projects may involve data with specific sensitivities, and we will work with Project Teams to address these concerns while maintaining the Initiative's principles of collaboration and accessibility.

The molecular data generated by the Initiative for the purpose of creating a reference database is generally not considered sensitive. However, if during the course of creating these data the Project Team determines that publishing specific data could cause demonstrable risk to organisational or jurisdictional operations, that data will be held privately until a mutually agreed resolution is reached.

If, during or after an embargo period, a Project Team considers data to be sensitive, they may request that the embargo be extended or that specific data be removed from public release while appropriate external processes are followed. Bioplatforms will act in good faith to support responsible data sharing, guided by the advice of Project Teams and collaborators. Analysed, non-sensitive outputs must still be made openly available, as per Section 3.3.2.

Similarly, metadata deemed sensitive (e.g., precise latitude and longitude coordinates of threatened species) will not be stored or published on the Bioplatforms Australia Data Portal. Instead, it will remain under the management of the Project Lead, who will be responsible for handling access requests as appropriate.

¹ <https://data.bioplatforms.com/>

² <https://www.qcif.edu.au/>

3.3. Data Sharing Schedule

Data sharing and collaborative interactions are encouraged to advance scientific discovery and maximise the value to the community of this Commonwealth Government National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS)-funded dataset.

3.3.1. Raw sequence data

Access to the raw sequence data (held in the Bioplatforms Australia Data Portal) will occur in two phases:

1. Mediated Access Phase:

- A data embargo will apply for up to 12 months from the creation date unless mutually agreed otherwise.
- During this phase, access is restricted to Project Teams (and their authorised users) to allow for first right of use and publication. The Bioplatforms Project Manager will manage this process.

2. Open Access Phase:

- After 12 months, data on the Bioplatforms Australia Data Portal will become openly available to all registered users (unless otherwise agreed).

3.3.2. Derived data products

Derived data products are datasets created through analysis of the raw data, including but not limited to:

- Reference genome assemblies
- Genome annotations
- Population genetics metrics
- Metabolite or protein profiles and compounds
- Taxonomic or functional profiles from metagenomic sequencing

Project Teams are responsible for making all derived data products openly available, within an agreed timeframe, using one of the following options:

1. **[Preferred]** Deposit in a recognised international repository (e.g. members of the [International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration](#)) to enhance discoverability and reuse.
2. Submit to the Bioplatforms Australia Data Portal, where access will follow the same timing and conditions as the Raw Data Open Access Phase (see Section 3.3.1).

4. Data and Metadata Retention

4.1. Retention

Regardless of whether data has been submitted to an agreed external repository, Bioplatforms will ensure that all data and metadata held on the Bioplatforms Australia Data Portal will be retained for the lifetime of the repository. This is currently defined by the operational horizon of Bioplatforms Australia.

4.2. Functional preservation

While every effort is made to ensure all data is accompanied by best-practice metadata, BioPlatforms Australia does not guarantee the accuracy, long-term usability or understandability of deposited objects over time.

4.3. Authenticity

All data files are stored with an MD5 checksum of their content. This checksum is used to verify that data downloaded from the BioPlatforms Australia Data Portal has been transferred without errors or corruption.

4.4. Succession plans

In the event of the closure of the BioPlatforms Australia Data Portal, best efforts will be made to migrate all content to suitable alternative repositories.

5. Data Use and Collaboration

All data created under this initiative is licensed under **Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY 4.0)**³.

The Initiative is committed to ensuring that the data and capabilities generated by the initiative are actively shared with and utilised by the scientific and wider community. General Data Users of the Initiative's data and capabilities are expected to uphold professional courtesy and maintain the highest standards of scientific integrity.

General Guidelines for Data Use

1. **Acknowledgment:** Ensure proper acknowledgment, as specified in Section 6, of the Initiative, BioPlatforms Australia, and any relevant contributors and/or funding bodies.
2. **Authorship:** Ensure appropriate authorship in line with the Project Team's contributions. If the data that is generated from other Projects forms a substantial part of your research, please discuss authorship opportunities with the relevant Project Leads.
3. **Data Citation:** Include appropriate citations for the datasets used, as specified in Section 6.
4. **Integrity:** Adhere to the highest standards of scientific integrity and ensure the data is used responsibly and respectfully.

Use of Data by Investigators Within or Outside the Consortium

- **Publication Status:** General Data Users of the Initiative's data, whether members of the Consortium or not, should be aware of the publication status (detailed in Section 3.3) of the data they are using. This can be found on the BioPlatforms Data Portal interface and the datasets metadata.
- **General Data Users:** General Data Users are free to use data generated by the initiative, as per the schedule in Section 3.3, provided they follow the Fort Lauderdale⁴ and Toronto Statement⁵ guidelines. Specifically:
 - Cite the source of the data and acknowledge the Project Partners and funders of the Initiative.

³ <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/deed.en>

⁴ <https://www.sanger.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/fortlauderdalereport.pdf>

⁵ <https://www.nature.com/articles/461168a.epdf>

- Recognise the interests of Project Partners in publishing reports on the generation and analysis of their data before external publications.
- Understand that datasets released to public databases as pre-publication data may remain unpublished until they appear in peer-reviewed publications.

The BioPlatforms Project Manager or Initiative Scientific Lead can facilitate communication with Project Team members to discuss collaborations.

6. Citation and Acknowledgment Information

6.1. Initiative Details

Please use the Initiative specific information found in Schedule 1 when publishing work using data from this Initiative.

6.2. Co-authorship Guidelines

The following serves as a guideline for determining the level of acknowledgment or co-authorship required when using the Initiative's data. There are two main groups to consider, and individuals may fall into one or both categories depending on their use at the time:

1. **Project Leads and Teams (Data Generators)** - those directly involved in generating the data.
 - The Project Lead and relevant team members should be appropriately credited based on their contributions.
 - Authorship for publications directly arising from the generation of Initiative data should be determined before project commencement in line with the NHMRC Authorship Guide (2019)⁶ and the CRediT (Contributor Roles Taxonomy) Framework⁷. BioPlatforms encourages projects to follow these frameworks to ensure fair and transparent attribution.
2. **General Data Users (Post-Project Use)** - those who access and use the data after it has been made available.
 - **Small, complementary dataset used** → Acknowledgment of the Initiative Consortium is required. Acknowledgment of individual Project Partners is not required.
 - **Moderate use of data (drawn from multiple Project Partners but not central to the publication)** → Acknowledgment of the Initiative Consortium is required. Relevant Project Partners should be contacted to discuss appropriate recognition.
 - **Significant portion of data used – integral to publication** → Acknowledgment of the Initiative Consortium is required, and co-authorship should be offered to the relevant Project Partners.

7. Communications

All communications (scientific or general publications and presentations) that arise from the Initiative Consortium's work will appropriately acknowledge the input of all relevant contributors. The publications

⁶ <https://www.nhmrc.gov.au/sites/default/files/documents/attachments/Authorship-Guide.pdf>

⁷ <https://credit.niso.org/>

should specify the collaborative nature of the project, and authorship is expected to include all those contributing significantly to the work (see Section 6).

Copies of communications are to be sent to the Initiative Project Manager (see details in Schedule 1) and the General Manager, Science Programs (Sarah Richmond, srichmond@bioplatforms.com) for collection and circulation to the Consortium as appropriate.

Schedule 1. The Australian Animal Disease Genomics Initiative

A. Purpose

The Australian Animal Disease Genomics Initiative is building a national genomics reference library for priority animal diseases. It uses next-generation sequencing technology and works with researchers, industry, and government to:

- Identify and characterise both known and novel animal pathogens and parasites
- Improve understanding of animal disease diversity, evolution, and adaptation
- Support surveillance, diagnostics, and the development of vaccines and treatments

B. Dataset Creation

This Initiative aims to generate the following data assets:

- Reference genomes and transcriptomes
- Genomic datasets for population and/or phylogenetic analyses
- Metagenomic datasets to characterise animal viromes

Other data types that may be generated include: Proteomic and metabolomic datasets to understand pathogen virulence.

C. The Australian Animal Disease Genomics Initiative Citation and Acknowledgment

Please use the below information when publishing work using data from this Initiative.

Project Information	
Bioplatforms Project Manager	Mabel Lum, mlum@bioplatforms.com
Bioplatforms Initiative DOI:	https://doi.org/10.25953/QZXV-MD52
Umbrella Bioproject ID:	PRJNA1217493 . <i>Please use this ID when submitting derived data to any database that is a member of the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (INSDC).</i>
Authors:	The Australian Animal Disease Genomics Initiative
Funding:	Supported by Bioplatforms Australia, enabled by the National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS), and the Australian Animal Disease Genomics Initiative Consortium
How to Cite:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General Initiative: <i>The Australian Animal Disease Genomics Initiative, 2025, https://doi.org/10.25953/QZXV-MD52</i> • Specific Dataset Use: <i>The Australian Animal Disease Genomics Initiative, 2025, https://doi.org/10.25953/QZXV-MD52, [year-of-data-download], [full dataset title], [dataset-access-URL], accessed [date-of-access].</i>
Acknowledging the Initiative Consortium:	<p>Please use the following statement: <i>We would like to acknowledge the contribution of the Australian Animal Disease Genomics Initiative Consortium in the generation of data used in this publication. The Initiative is supported by funding from Bioplatforms Australia, enabled by the Commonwealth Government National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS).</i></p> <p>If relevant, also credit other organisations involved in collection of the particular dataset you are using (as listed in 'project_lead' and 'project_collaborators' in the metadata record).</p>